

Intelligent Techniques Applied to Security in Microservice Architecture

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Review Protocol	1
2.1	Research Questions	1
2.2	Search Procedure	2
2.3	Study Selection	3
2.4	Keywording of Abstracts	4
2.5	Data Extraction and Mapping	4
2.6	Threats to validity	5
3	Report the Review	7
A	List of Primary Studies	9
B	Technical Report	13
B.1	Results	13
B.1.1	RQ 1: What are the application domains that have benefited from defense solutions?	13
B.1.2	RQ 2: What types of attacks and/or vulnerabilities are addressed in the proposed solution?	16
B.1.3	RQ 3: What defense strategies are adopted for the detection and/or mitigation of malicious actions in applications?	18
B.1.4	RQ 4: What intelligent techniques were addressed for the detection of attacks and/or vulnerabilities in applications?	21
B.1.5	RQ 5: What datasets were used to train the intelligent solutions?	22

1 Introduction

The purpose of this study is to provide a comprehensive and unbiased overview of intelligent techniques applied to security in microservice architectures. To achieve this objective, the Systematic Mapping Study (SMS) technique was adopted, as proposed by Evidence-Based Software Engineering (EBSE). The SMS will be conducted in accordance with the process defined by [Petersen et al. \(2015\)](#), which can be summarized in five steps:

- **Step 1 – Definition of Research Questions.** This step reports the research objectives for this systematic mapping. In short, a research protocol must have a predetermined plan that describes research questions and guides how the systematic mapping must be conducted;
- **Step 2 – Conduction of Search.** This step describes how the primary studies must be searched and identified;
- **Step 3 – Screening of Papers.** This step reports how the identified studies must be evaluated according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria defined in this protocol;
- **Step 4 – Keywording of Abstracts.** This step shows how the included studies must be analyzed and classified; and
- **Step 5 – Data Extraction and Mapping of Studies.** This step describes how the final representation must be built, based on the final scheme created in Step 4.

2 Review Protocol

This section delineates the protocol of the proposed SMS. In essence, a research protocol constitutes a predetermined plan that outlines the research questions and provides a guide to facilitate the execution of the study. The essential process steps of a systematic mapping study are as follows: (i) definition of research questions; (ii) conducting the search for relevant papers; (iii) screening of papers; (iv) keywording of abstracts; (v) data extraction and mapping; and (vi) threats of validity. Next, we reported a description of each step.

2.1 Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to identify primary studies that report evidence on intelligent techniques applied to security in microservice architectures. In other words, the main objective of this SMS is to identify primary studies that propose solutions using intelligent techniques to detect and mitigate threats and vulnerabilities in microservice-based applications. To do so, we established five research questions (RQ):

RQ1: What are the application domains that have benefited from defense solutions? The objective of this question is to identify the application domains that have proposed or used solutions for identifying attacks and/or vulnerabilities. For example: IoT Systems, Web Applications, Cloud Systems, among others.

RQ2: What types of attacks and/or vulnerabilities are addressed in the proposed solutions? The purpose of this question is to understand what types of attacks and/or vulnerabilities were addressed by the solution. For example: brute-force attacks, code injection attacks, denial-of-service attacks, among others.

RQ3: What intelligent techniques were used to detect attacks and/or vulnerabilities in applications? The objective of this question is to identify the intelligent techniques used to detect attacks and/or vulnerabilities. For example: machine learning, neural networks, deep learning, federated learning, among others.

RQ4: What defense techniques are used to detect attacks and/or vulnerabilities in applications? The objective of this question is to identify the defense techniques used to detect attacks and/or vulnerabilities. For example: secure communication management, cryptographic key management, best practices, among others.

RQ5: What datasets were used to train the intelligent solutions? The objective of this research question is to identify which datasets were used to train the intelligent solutions, and whether they are private or public.

2.2 Search Procedure

Considering the RQs presented in [Section 2.1](#), we defined the search strategy, which is composed of source selection criteria, sources list, studies language, and keywords and their related terms.

- *Sources selection criteria:* We adopted the following criteria to select search sources (i.e., publication databases and search engines) to find primary studies: (i) content update (i.e., publications are regularly updated); (ii) availability (i.e., the full text of the papers are available); (iii) quality of results (i.e., the accuracy of the results returned by the search); and (iv) versatility to export the results (i.e., since much information are returned through the search, a mechanism to export the results is required) ([Dieste et al., 2009](#));
- *Source list:* The publication database selected for this study was Scopus¹ because of its broad coverage and relevance in the fields of computer science and software engineering, being widely recognized as a comprehensive source of peer-reviewed literature ([Petersen](#)

¹<http://www.scopus.com>

et al., 2015). To minimize the risk of omitting relevant studies, we also applied the backward snowballing technique to the selected papers (i.e., second phase), incorporating the additional results as gray literature in our SMS (Petersen et al., 2015).

- *Studies language*: Only primary studies written in English will be considered in this systematic mapping, since it is the most common language in scientific papers;
- *Keywords*: “microservice”, “security”, and “machine learning”, with the following related terms:
 - **microservice**: “micro service”, “micro services”, “micro-service”, “micro-services”, “microservice”, “microservices”
 - **security**: “security”, “self-protecting”, “self-protection”, “self-safety”, “self-securing”, “self-security”
 - **machine learning**: “machine learning”, “ai”, “artificial intelligence”, “dataset”
- *Search string*: As we identified three terms related to known keywords to answer the RQs, we used the Boolean operator OR to link the main terms and their synonyms, and the Boolean operator AND to combine these terms, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Search string

(“micro service” OR “micro services” OR “micro-service” OR “micro-services“ OR “microservice“ OR “microservices“)
AND
(“security” OR “self-protecting” OR “self-protection” OR “self-safety” OR “self-securing” OR “self-security”)
AND
(“machine learning” OR “ai” OR “artificial intelligence” OR “dataset”)

2.3 Study Selection

Another important element of planning is defining the inclusion criteria (IC) and the exclusion criteria (EC). These criteria enable us to include primary studies relevant to answering the research questions and exclude those that do not. In other words, if a primary study satisfies the IC established in this section, researchers include it, and if it satisfies one or more EC, they exclude it. To do so, we defined one inclusion criterion for our SMS, namely:

- **IC1**: The study presents evidence of a solution that uses some intelligent technique to provide security to a microservice-based application.

The exclusion criteria established are:

- **EC1:** The study does not provide evidence of a solution that uses some intelligent technique to deal with security in a microservice-based application.
- **EC2:** The study is an editorial, position paper, keynote speech, opinion, tutorial, poster, or panel;
- **EC3:** The study is not written in English;
- **EC4:** The study only provides a summary or is not available in full-length;
- **EC5:** The study is similar to previous work developed by the same author. Here, only the most recent study or the most complete version must be considered; and
- **EC6:** The study is a secondary study.

2.4 Keywording of Abstracts

[Figure 1](#) summarizes the phases of conducting the study and the number of studies selected for this study. In the **Search Phase**, the terms defined for this investigation were combined to create the search string applied to the Scopus database. This search returned 320 studies. In the **Filter Application** phase, studies that did not meet the primary research criteria were excluded (**Filter 1**), resulting in 77 studies remaining (**Filter 2**). After applying the predefined selection criteria, **Filter 3** retained 36 studies for full-text reading. Any disagreements regarding inclusion or exclusion were resolved through discussion among the review participants to ensure consistency in the selection process. After a thorough analysis of the full texts of the 36 studies, all were included in the final set of studies for this tertiary research. [Appendix A](#) presents the list of primary studies selected in our mapping.

To increase the reliability of our results, we reviewed all the studies selected before proceeding to the data synthesis ([Kitchenham and Charters, 2007](#)). The forms (see [Table 2 – Section 2.5](#)) filled in the second selection were analyzed again and, whenever necessary, important parts of each study or its full text were read to identify potential classification errors. During the review, we extracted more information from some studies, particularly the ones that did not have enough information extracted in the previous step, and did not remove any study, maintaining the 36 primary studies selected.

2.5 Data Extraction and Mapping

During the data collection phase, we will collect a set of variables that describe each primary study. Data collection is going to be handled by members of the team and conflicts will be resolved by a supervisor. Each researcher involved will perform data extraction for every primary study separately. Then the two values of each variable obtained by each researcher will be compared to each other and the final value of the variable will be assigned to the primary study

Table 2: Data Extraction Form

Research Topic	Value	RQ
Study ID	Integer Value	–
Title	Article Title	–
Author Name	Author Names	–
Year	Publication Year	–
Publication Database	Name of the publication database	—
Application Domains	Domain and/or subdomain where the study is inserted	RQ1
Attack Type	Name of the attack	RQ2
Defense Strategies	Name of the defense strategy	RQ3
AI Techniques	Name of the AI techniques	RQ4
Dataset	Name and availability of the dataset	RQ5

Zavala et al., 2019). Next, a description of the threats of our study is reported:

Omission of papers. As reported in Section 2.2, one publication database was used to extract the data analyzed in this paper. According to Dybå et al. (2007), Kitchenham and Charters (2007), and Petersen et al. (2015), Scopus database is sufficient and the most relevant source in the software engineering area, since it indexes studies from other database publications. Despite our efforts to make this process as reliable as possible, it is still possible that primary studies were missed and not reported. Although we have conducted evaluations to calibrate and ensure the efficiency of our search string, our study depends on the publication database’s search engine. Thus, in order to minimize problems in the search phase, we adapted the general search string to meet the publication database’s constraints and limitations.

Reviewers’ reliability. Only one researcher was responsible for the conduct of our study, which can result in a bias risk. To ensure the reliability and unbiased nature of our study, AI, security, and software engineering specialists supported the researchers during the conduction meeting, answering questions about the inclusion or exclusion of studies. Moreover, none of the included primary studies came from our research group or our associated researchers. Therefore, we are unaware of any potential biases introduced during the analysis.

Data extraction. We have analyzed or interpreted data extracted from the primary studies because not all data was clear. Since this activity involves human judgment, we rigorously followed our research protocol (see Section 2.2), and defined a form for data extraction based on our RQs. Thus, to ensure the validity of our study, we analyzed other information sources, such as technical reports, websites, and manuals.

Replicability. We report the process used to conduct the mapping in [Section 2.2](#) to make our study replicable. Since we are using electronic databases to collect all data and these databases are constantly being updated, the results might not be identical in a future search. Therefore, replicating this mapping can be considered a not trivial task, but the periodic update can assist the stakeholders in monitoring and evolution of a research area.

3 Report the Review

We will report the following items in our study: (i) discuss findings: we will report the description of primary studies, results of any quantitative summaries, and details of any meta-analysis; (ii) present a discussion: we will summarize the principal findings, strengths and weaknesses of the mapping, and the meaning of findings, such as applicability, benefits, adverse effects, and risks; (iii) discuss conclusions: we will report the recommendations, such as practical implications for software development, implications for practitioners, and unanswered questions and implications for future research; and (iv) discuss limitations: we will synthesize the limitations of this study.

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A List of Primary Studies

Table 3 lists the primary studies included in this SMS. The ID column presents the study identifiers. The Reference column displays the author(s) and title, along with an external link to the online reference for each study. Finally, the Year column shows the publication years of the studies.

Table 3: List of Primary Studies

ID	Reference	Year
S1	Ficco, Massimo M. and Fusco, Pietro and Guerriero, Antonio and Pietrantuono, Roberto and Russo, M. and Palmieri, Francesco and Russo, Stefano, A Benchmark for DDoS Attacks Detection in Microservice Architectures.	2025
S2	Joraviya, Nidhi and Gohil, Bhavesh N. and Rao, Udai Pratap, Ab-HIDS: An anomaly-based host intrusion detection system using frequency of N-gram system call features and ensemble learning for containerized environment.	2024
S3	Tsegaye, Henok Berhanu and Tshakwanda, Petro Mushidi and Devetsikiotis, Michael and Spachos, Petros, A Cloud-Edge Microservices Architecture for Smart Healthcare: SDN-Based Medical Asset Management.	2025
S4	He, Weizhen and Tan, Jinglei and Guo, Yunfei and Shang, Ke and Zhang, Hengwei, A Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Deception Asset Selection Algorithm in Differential Games.	2024
S5	Caviglione, Luca and Guarascio, Massimo and Pisani, Francesco Sergio and Zuppelli, Marco, A Few to Unveil Them All: Leveraging Mixture of Experts on Minimal Data for Detecting Covert Channels in Containerized Cloud Infrastructures.	2024
S6	Mittal, Akshay, AI-Augmented DevSecOps Pipelines for Secure and Scalable Service-Oriented Architectures in Cloud-Native Systems.	2025
S7	Park, Heeji and El Azzaoui, Abir E. and Park, Jong Hyuk (James J.), AIDS-Based Cyber Threat Detection Framework for Secure Cloud-Native Microservices.	2025
S8	Ying, Fei and Wang, Jia and Lan, Dapeng and Zhang, Jialin and Zhan, Ming and Zhao, Shengjie, AI-Enhanced Mimic Defense for Securing Microservices-Based Consumer Unmanned Systems.	2025
S9	Sever, Yigit and Ekinici, Goktug and Dogan, Adnan Harun and Alparslan, Bugra and Gurbuz, Abdurrahman Said and Jabrayilov, Vahab and Angin, Pelin, An Empirical Analysis of IDS Approaches in Container Security.	2022

Continued on next page

ID	Reference	Year
S10	Moreira, Rodrigo and da Silva Villaça, Rodolfo S. and Ribeiro, Moises R.N. and Martins, Joberto S.B. and Correa, João Henrique G.M. and Carvalho, Tereza Cristina Melo De Brito and Silva, Flávio De Oliveira, An intelligent native network slicing security architecture empowered by federated learning.	2025
S11	Kohyarnejadfar, Iman and Aloise, Daniel and Azhari, Seyed Vahid and Dagenais, Michel R., Anomaly detection in microservice environments using distributed tracing data analysis and NLP.	2022
S12	Zhou, Zhaoxiong, A Novel Anti-DDoS Microservice Load Balancing Scheme Based on Improved GBDT Algorithm.	2024
S13	Gaspard, Baye and Hussain, Alaa and Oracevic, Alma and Hussain, Rasheed and Ahsan Kazmi, Syed Muhammad Raza, API Security in Large Enterprises: Leveraging Machine Learning for Anomaly Detection.	2021
S14	Sowmya, M. and Rai, Ankith J. and Spoorthi, V. and Irfan, Mohammed and Honnavalli, Prasad B. and Nagasundari, S., API Traffic Anomaly Detection in Microservice Architecture.	2023
S15	Variant Wahono, Bari Hade and Asfihani, null and Mahfud, Ilyas and Exshadi, Baskworo Yoga Indra and Shiddiqi, Ary Mazharuddin, Brute Force Detection System Based on Machine Learning Classifier Algorithm in Cloud-Based Infrastructure.	2024
S16	Verkerken, Miel and Santos, José and D'hooge, Laurens and Wauters, Tim and Volckaert, Bruno and de Turck, Filip D., ChronosGuards: A Hierarchical Machine Learning Intrusion Detection System for Modern Clouds.	2024
S17	Sappa, Ankita, Context-Aware Security Policies for Data-Driven Applications in Cloud-Native Architectures.	2025
S18	Guo, Zhiwei and Yu, Keping and Lyu, Zhihan and Choo, Kim Kwang Raymond and Shi, Peng and Rodrigues, Joel J.P.C., Deep Federated Learning Enhanced Secure POI Microservices for Cyber-Physical Systems.	2022
S19	Castro, Jessica and Laranjeiro, Nuno and Vieira, Marco Paulo Amorim, Detecting DoS Attacks in Microservice Applications: Approach and Case Study.	2022
S20	Castro, Jessica and Laranjeiro, Nuno and Goseva - Popstojanova, Katerina and Vieira, Marco Paulo Amorim, Developing Attack Detection Models for Microservice Applications: A Comprehensive Framework and Its Illustration and Validation on DoS Attacks.	2025

ID	Reference	Year
S21	Chen, Ziyue and Kong, He and Ding, Shuai and Lv, Quanfeng and Wei, Guo, Efficient DDoS Detection and Mitigation in Cloud Data Centers Using eBPF and XDP.	2024
S22	Araujo, Iury and Vieira, Marco Paulo Amorim, Enhancing intrusion detection in containerized services: Assessing machine learning models and an advanced representation for system call data.	2025
S23	Darwesh, Ghadeer and Hammoud, Jaafar and Vorobeva, Alisa A., Enhancing Kubernetes security with machine learning: a proactive approach to anomaly detection.	2024
S24	Deng, Yong, Enhancing Microservice Security Through Middleware Architecture: A Machine Learning Approach.	2025
S25	Araujo, Iury and Antunes, Nuno and Vieira, Marco Paulo Amorim, Evaluation of Machine Learning for Intrusion Detection in Microservice Applications.	2023
S26	Castro, Jessica and Laranjeiro, Nuno and Vieira, Marco Paulo Amorim, Generating Realistic Attack Data for Microservices: Framework and Case Study.	2023
S27	Chen, Jiyu and Huang, Heqing and Chen, Hao, Informer: Irregular traffic detection for containerized microservices RPC in the real world.	2022
S28	Yan, Yikuan and Huang, Keman and Siegel, Michael D., ISSF: An Intelligent Security Service Framework for Cloud-native Operations.	2025
S29	Zhu, Xianfeng and Lu, Renmeng and Li, Xun and Zhang, Guangyi and Pan, Lijun, Methods for Correlation Analysis of Alarm Information in Multi-Microservice Application Environments.	2024
S30	Zuppelli, Marco and Guarascio, Massimo and Caviglione, Luca and Liguori, Angelica, No Country for Leaking Containers: Detecting Exfiltration of Secrets Through AI and Syscalls.	2024
S31	Almi'ani, Muder M. and AbuGhazleh, Alia and Jararweh, Yaser I. and Razaque, A., Resilient Back Propagation Neural Network Security Model For Containerized Cloud Computing.	2022
S32	Abdennebi, Anes and Nadjia, Kara and Lahlou, Laaziz and Younis, Mohamed F. and Ould-Slimane, Hakima, Sec-Llama: A Compact Fine-Tuned LLM for Network Intrusion Detection in Kubernetes Clusters.	2025
S33	Kadiyala, Sai Praveen and Li, Xiaolan and Lee, Wonjun and Catlin, Andrew, Securing Microservices Against Password Guess Attacks using Hardware Performance Counters.	2022

ID	Reference	Year
S34	Tunde-Onadele, Olufogorehan and Lin, Yuhang and Gu, Xiaohui and He, Jingzhu and Latapie, Hugo M., Self-Supervised Machine Learning Framework for Online Container Security Attack Detection.	2024
S35	Chen, Yong Syuan and Lien, Hsiang Yin and Li, Joyu and Lin, Chia Yu, Supervised Intrusion Detection with Out-of-Distribution Detection for Microservices.	2024
S36	Viswanathan, Jayaraj and Dinesh Kumar, N. and Kumar, S. Udhaya, Zero Trust Security for Web Applications in Microservice-Based Environments.	2024

B Technical Report

The purpose of this section is to present the objective results derived from the research questions defined in Section 2.1 and to provide a comprehensive overview of the approaches that employ intelligent methods for the detection and/or mitigation of malicious actions in microservice-based applications.

In this context, intelligent methods refer to the application of supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning techniques aimed at identifying attacks and vulnerabilities within this architectural paradigm.

B.1 Results

To present the demographic data of the investigation conducted, Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of the selected studies over the period covered by this systematic mapping. Based on the distribution shown, it is possible to observe a progressive increase in the number of published studies in recent years, particularly within the period from 2021 to 2025. This pattern suggests a growing consolidation of research efforts in this domain. It is worth emphasizing that this distribution specifically encompasses studies that proposed solutions for the detection or mitigation of malicious actions supported by artificial intelligence in microservice-based applications. Furthermore, it should be noted that, in this interpretation, the year 2025 represents a partial year within this mapping, since the database search was conducted in the third week of November.

In Figure 3, the distribution of the studies included in this SMS is illustrated according to their publication venue, characterizing the second analytical perspective of a study of this nature. To this end, the studies selected in this SMS (see Appendix A) were classified into five types, namely: Conference, Journal, Symposium, and *Workshop*. As can be observed, there is a concentration of studies published in *Conference* (14) and *Journal* (17), totaling 31 studies. This distribution indicates that the studies were disseminated through publication venues that typically require more mature results in terms of both the proposed approach and its evaluation.

Next, we report the results of the investigation conducted, organized according to the research questions established in the research protocol (see Section 2).

B.1.1 RQ 1: What are the application domains that have benefited from defense solutions?

This research question aimed to identify the application domains that implemented security solutions in microservice-based systems and that employ some intelligent technique to detect and/or mitigate malicious actions. As illustrated in Figure 4, six application domains were identified, namely: Microservices (Generic Domain), Containers and Orchestration, Cloud Computing, Cyber-Physical Systems, Web Applications, and Networks and Telecommunications. The

Figure 2: Distribution of Studies by Year of Publication.

Figure 3: Distribution of Studies by Type of Publication.

first domain accounts for 36.11% of the analyzed studies, representing the most recurrent environment among the evaluated works. The second domain corresponds to 27.78% of the studies. The third, related to cloud computing, represents 19.44% of the investigations, whereas the fourth and fifth domains were addressed in 5.56% of the studies each. The sixth domain corresponds to 2.78%, with only a single study identified. Next, the definitions of each identified domain are presented. The first domain accounts for 36.11% of the analyzed studies, representing

the most recurrent environment among the evaluated works. The second domain corresponds to 27.78% of the studies. The third, related to cloud computing, represents 19.44% of the investigations, whereas the fourth and fifth domains were addressed in 5.56% of the studies each. The sixth domain corresponds to 2.78%, with only a single study identified.

Next, the definitions of each identified domain are presented.

Figure 4: Number of Studies by Application Domain

1. **Microservices (Generic Domain).** This domain is adopted when the study is not associated with a specific sector but focuses directly on the microservice architectural style. The works typically address intelligent monitoring solutions, self-protection tools, and observability and security mechanisms applicable to different types of distributed applications. A total of 13 studies were included in this domain (S1, S7, S11, S12, S14, S19, S20, S24, S25, S26, S29, S33, S35).
2. **Containers and Orchestration.** This domain encompasses technologies such as Docker, Kubernetes, and OpenShift, which are used for packaging, isolation, and management of distributed services. Studies in this category frequently investigate container escape, anomalies in syscall invocations, and distributed attacks, including DDoS executed by PoDs (*Proof of Delivery*) in orchestrated clusters. A total of 10 studies were included in this domain (S2, S5, S9, S22, S23, S27, S30, S31, S32, S34).
3. **Cloud Computing.** This domain comprises *serverless* architectures, *multi-tenant* platforms, and distributed infrastructures used to host large-scale applications. The studies typically analyze risks such as API-based intrusion and isolation failures, which are common in shared and highly elastic environments. Seven studies were included in this domain (S4, S5, S15, S16, S17, S21, S28).

4. **Sistemas Ciberfísicos.** Este domínio inclui aplicações presentes em manufatura, robótica, veículos autônomos e *smart grids*. Os estudos normalmente analisam requisitos de sincronização, comunicação em tempo real e mecanismos de segurança adequados a ambientes fortemente integrados entre componentes físicos e computacionais. Três estudos foram incluídos neste domínio (E3, E8, E18).
5. **Web Applications.** This domain encompasses traditional web applications, portals, e-commerce systems, and services based on REST or GraphQL APIs. Studies in this category frequently explore threats related to authentication and authorization, broken access control, and injection attacks, which are typical characteristics of systems with intensive client–server interaction. Two studies were included in this domain (S13, S36).
6. **Networks and Telecommunications.** This domain encompasses studies focused on Software-Defined Networking (*SDN*), 5G technologies, and Network Functions Virtualization (*NFV*). The works commonly investigate aspects related to orchestration and traffic flow management, which are fundamental to the operation of modern communication infrastructures. Only one study was identified in this domain (S10).

B.1.2 RQ 2: What types of attacks and/or vulnerabilities are addressed in the proposed solution?

This research question aimed to identify the types of attacks and/or security vulnerabilities addressed in microservice-based systems that employ intelligent techniques to detect and/or mitigate malicious actions. As illustrated in [Figure 5](#), ten types of attacks or malicious actions were identified. Behavioral Anomalies were identified in 50.00% of the studies. Traffic or Network Flow Anomalies were identified in 36.11% of the studies. Arbitrary Code Execution was identified in 27.78% of the studies. Information Leakage or Exfiltration was identified in 22.22% of the studies. Web Attacks and Denial-of-Service Attacks were identified in 19.44% of the studies each. Password Brute-Force Attacks were identified in 8.33% of the studies. Resource Exhaustion and Generic attacks were identified in 5.56% of the studies each. Finally, Privilege Escalation or Unauthorized Access was identified in 2.78% of the studies. It is important to emphasize that some studies propose approaches capable of mitigating more than one type of attack or malicious action. For this reason, the total number of identified attack types exceeds the number of primary studies selected in this mapping. Next, the definitions of each identified attack or malicious action are presented in alphabetical order.

- **Behavioral Anomalies.** This category encompasses situations in which the system identifies behaviors that deviate from the normal pattern, even without necessarily associating them with a specific type of attack. It includes pattern changes, deviations in metrics such as CPU, network, and I/O usage, unusual interactions among microservices, and anomalies not classified as Web attacks or DDoS, including potential *zero-day* scenarios. The

Figure 5: Distribution of Studies by Type of Attack

studies S3, S5, S6, S7, S8, S10, S11, S13, S18, S22, S24, S28, S29, S30, S31, S34, S35, and S36 were included in this attack type.

- **Traffic or Network Flow Anomalies.** This category encompasses unexpected changes in communication between services, such as anomalies in RPC interactions, abrupt variations in traffic volume, irregular flows, and unusual traffic patterns. These situations indicate deviations in the normal data flow within the distributed architecture. The studies S5, S8, S9, S10, S11, S14, S16, S21, S27, S28, S29, S31, and S32 were included in this attack type.
- **Execução Arbitrária de Código.** Refere-se a ataques em que o invasor consegue executar comandos, scripts ou código no ambiente alvo, geralmente explorando vulnerabilidades que comprometem a integridade e o controle do sistema. Isso inclui tanto execução remota quanto injeção de cargas maliciosas. Foi incluído nos estudos E2, E9, E16, E22, E25, E26, E30, E31, E32, E34 nesta categoria.
- **Information Leakage or Exfiltration.** This category encompasses attacks in which the adversary gains unauthorized access to sensitive data, capturing secrets, extracting confidential information, or exposing protected content. The studies S2, S9, S16, S22, S25, S26, S30, and S34 were included in this attack type.
- **Web Attacks.** This category encompasses attacks targeting the application layer, including SQL *Injection*, malicious file upload, parameter manipulation, unauthorized access via HTTP, and exploitation of vulnerabilities in APIs. The studies S2, S13, S16, S24, S25, S26, and S36 were included in this attack type.

- **Denial-of-Service Attacks.** This category encompasses attacks whose objective is to degrade or disrupt a service through the massive submission of traffic, requests, or operations that exhaust CPU, memory, disk, or network resources. It includes *flooding* attacks, volumetric attacks, and total or partial infrastructure exhaustion. Seven studies addressing this type of attack were identified (S1, S12, S19, S20, S21, S23, S32).
- **Password Brute-Force Attacks.** This category refers to repetitive and systematic authentication attempts using multiple password combinations until correct access is achieved. Three studies addressing this type of attack were identified (S15, S33, S36).
- **Resource Overload.** This category represents attacks that provoke excessive resource consumption, often simulating legitimate behavior. It includes CPU abuse, malicious saturation of *threads*, massive creation of connections, and requests that mimic real *workloads*, resulting in performance degradation. This type of attack was identified in two studies (S12 and S23).
- **Generic.** This category is applied to studies that address attacks in a broad manner, without specifying a particular technique or threat. It typically reflects the absence of adequate monitoring and detection mechanisms, allowing malicious activities to go unnoticed. The studies S4 and S17 were classified under this attack type.
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B.1.3 RQ 3: What defense strategies are adopted for the detection and/or mitigation of malicious actions in applications?

This research question aimed to identify defense strategies, grounded in intelligent techniques, for the detection and/or mitigation of malicious actions in microservice-based systems. As illustrated in [Figure 6](#), the strategies were grouped into nine categories, organized according to their operational purpose. Among them, the Behavioral Modeling category presented the highest recurrence in the analyzed studies, totaling 55.56%. The Traffic Monitoring category was identified in 25.00% of the studies, whereas *Syscall* Monitoring was identified in 22.22% of the studies.

The *Middleware* Inspection, Observability and Telemetry, and Governance and Security Policies strategies were identified in 13.89%, 11.11%, and 5.56% of the studies, respectively. Finally, the Orchestration and Hardening, Secrets Management and Protection, and Load Control and Distribution techniques were identified in 2.78% of the studies each. It is important to emphasize that some studies report more than one strategy in their initiatives for the detection and/or mitigation of threats and vulnerabilities in microservice-based applications. Next,

detailed definitions of each category are presented, following the order of occurrence shown in the aforementioned figure.

Figure 6: Defense Strategies Adopted in the Studies

- Behavioral Monitoring.** This category encompasses techniques that learn and identify normal operational patterns of the application, thereby enabling the detection of behavioral deviations that may indicate threats. It represents a generic and adaptive mechanism applied in distributed architectures with the objective of recognizing anomalous variations in interactions and operational flows among microservices. This approach was identified in the studies S5, S7, S8, S9, S10, S13, S15, S26, S18, S20, S22, S25, S26, S28, S30, S31, S32, S33, S34, and S35.

Traffic Monitoring. This category encompasses techniques based on the processing and active analysis of traffic between microservices, with the objective of inspecting requests, communication patterns, and potential anomalies. The studies classified under this category investigate vulnerabilities and risks associated with data transmission among services, including the detection of deviations, interceptions, and atypical behaviors. The studies S1, S8, S10, S14, S16, S19, S21, S27, and S32 were included in this category.

Syscall Monitoring. This category encompasses techniques focused on the analysis and interpretation of system calls performed by microservices. By examining these internal calls, it is possible to identify the actual behavior of the application, detect unusual actions, understand interactions at the operating system level, and identify potential abuses

or attacks. This defense technique was identified in the studies S2, S9, S16, S22, S25, S30, S33, and S34.

Inspection Middleware. This category consists of the use of an intermediate layer that operates directly in the security domain by inspecting or mediating communication between microservices to ensure integrity, confidentiality, and compliance. Such middleware may enforce additional validations, apply security policies, and perform active filtering, thereby contributing to the reduction of risks associated with internal traffic. The studies S1, S3, S13, S24, and S36 were classified under this category.

Observability and Telemetry. This category involves the use of metrics, logs, distributed *tracing*, and other telemetry mechanisms as core elements of the defense strategy. The objective is to provide deep visibility into the execution of microservices, thereby enabling the identification of failures, anomalies, and vulnerabilities based on the observed system behavior. This technique was identified in the studies S3, S11, S28, and S29.

Governance and Security Policies. This category encompasses practices related to the establishment of rules, validation policies, and governance mechanisms that ensure the secure operation of microservice environments. It includes secure pipelines, configuration validations, and architectural guidelines aimed at preventing improper resource usage and reducing misconfiguration risks. Two studies were classified under this category (S6 and S17).

Orchestration and Hardening. This category refers to protection mechanisms applied at the cluster level, including Kubernetes hardening and strategies aimed at strengthening orchestration security. It involves structural controls, robust configurations, and practices designed to reduce the attack surface in container-based platforms. This category was identified in study S23.

Secrets Management and Protection. This category encompasses practices and mechanisms aimed at protecting sensitive information, secrets, and encrypted data used by microservices. It includes secure management of keys, secrets, and credentials, ensuring privacy, access control, and resilience against exfiltration attempts or misuse. One study was classified under this category (S36).

Load Control and Distribution. This category encompasses approaches that leverage load balancing as a defensive mechanism, distributing traffic efficiently in order to prevent overload and maintain application stability. This strategy contributes to resilience and fault mitigation by preventing a single service or node from becoming a critical point of failure. Only one study was classified under this category (S12).

B.1.4 RQ 4: What intelligent techniques were addressed for the detection of attacks and/or vulnerabilities in applications?

This research question aims to identify the intelligent techniques applied to the real-time detection of attacks or malicious actions, considering systems designed based on the microservice architecture. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of the studies according to the AI techniques identified in this investigation. With twenty-six studies (72.22%), Classical Machine Learning appears as the most recurrent technique among the analyzed works. Deep Learning follows with seven studies (19.44%), while Federated Learning was identified in two studies (5.56%). Finally, Large Language Models and Reinforcement Learning were each identified in one study, representing 2.78% per category. Regarding this distribution, it is important to emphasize that some studies employed more than one AI technique. Next, the definitions of each technique are presented.

Figure 7: Distribution of AI Techniques Across the Selected Studies.

- **Classical Machine Learning.** This category encompasses traditional supervised and unsupervised learning methods, including algorithms such as Random Forest, XGBoost, GBDT, Decision Trees, SVM, Logistic Regression, KNN, Naive Bayes, and statistical approaches. It is applied when studies employ classical classifiers for anomaly detection, traffic classification, or identification of malicious patterns. This technique was identified in the studies S1, S2, S6, S7, S9, S11, S12, S13, S14, S15, S16, S17, S19, S20, S21, S22, S23, S24, S25, S26, S28, S29, S30, S33, S35, and S36.
- **Deep Learning.** This category encompasses architectures based on deep neural networks, such as MLP, CNN, LSTM, GRU, Autoencoders, Transformers applied to detection tasks, Informer models, and advanced sequential models. These approaches are widely used to capture temporal, spatial, or hierarchical dependencies in traffic flows, service calls, and

time-series data, thereby enabling the identification of complex patterns and sophisticated attacks. This technique was identified in the studies S3, S5, S8, S18, S27, S31, and S34.

- **Federated Learning.** This category involves distributed training strategies without direct data sharing, including horizontal, vertical, and collaborative approaches. It is employed in scenarios that require privacy preservation and support for distributed infrastructures, such as 5G networks, *slicing*, and *multi-cloud* systems. This technique was identified in the studies S10 and S18.
- **Large Language Models.** This category encompasses the use of large-scale Large Language Models, such as LLaMA, BERT, GPT, specialized Transformers, and MoE architectures adapted through *fine-tuning*. It is applied when the study directly relies on established models, reusing their capabilities for tasks such as classification, traffic analysis, or anomaly detection. This technique was identified in study S32.
- **Reinforcement Learning.** This category encompasses methods based on the interaction between agent, environment, and reward function, including Deep Reinforcement Learning, Q-Learning, DQN, differential games, and dynamic strategies driven by Reinforcement Learning. It is applied when sequential decision-making is required for adaptive defense, active detection, or automated response to threats in microservice architectures. This technique was identified in study S4.

B.1.5 RQ 5: What datasets were used to train the intelligent solutions?

This research question sought to gather evidence regarding the datasets used to train the intelligent models in the evaluated studies, with the objective of understanding the availability of these datasets. Figure 8 illustrates the distribution of the datasets identified in the literature and their frequency of use across the studies. As can be observed, Unavailable Datasets were the most recurrent among the studies included in this mapping, totaling 22 studies (61.11%). Available Datasets were identified in twelve studies (33.33%), while studies in which the use of a dataset for training was not applicable were identified in two studies (5.56%). Next, information regarding the characteristics of each dataset category is presented.

- **Unavailable Datasets.** Studies that created their own datasets and did not make them publicly available were classified under this category. In summary, these studies reported only the characteristics of the dataset and the results obtained during the training processes. Unavailable datasets stood out, corresponding to twenty-two studies (S3, S5, S6, S7, S8, S9, S11, S12, S13, S17, S19, S23, S24, S26, S27, S29, S30, S32, S33, S34, S35, S36).
- **Available Datasets.** This category encompasses studies that made the datasets used publicly available. Twelve studies (S1, S2, S10, S14, S15, S16, S18, S20, S21, S22, S25, and

Figure 8: Distribution of Studies by Identified Datasets.

S31) were classified under this category.

- **Not Applicable.** This category comprises studies in which the use of datasets is not applicable to the intelligent model development process. The two studies (S4 and S28) classified under this category employed Reinforcement Learning.